

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND PLACE OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the national concept of the inclusive education model, the uniqueness of this model in terms of its modernity and universality, the problems of ensuring continuity in the education of children with disabilities in the educational system have been discussed.

Keywords:... inclusive education, disabled, social protection, model, project, concept, audio books,

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Inclusive education is a process of educational development, a new form of education that assumes the universality of education, provides education for all children based on their different needs, and provides education for children with disabilities. Inclusive education is the process of integrating children with disabilities into the educational process and adapting the educational system to children with disabilities, with social justice and equality as the main goal.

The mission of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and circumstances. At the same time, the principle of inclusion implies that children with limited opportunities should live in a family and study together with their peers in a regular school in order to have a positive mental and social development. Inclusive education seeks to develop a child-centered methodology and all children recognizes that there are individuals with different needs in education, in the educational process. Such education seeks to develop an approach to teaching and learning that is conducive to meeting these diverse needs in the teaching process. If teaching and learning become more effective as a result of the changes introduced by inclusive education, this is the achievement and success of all children. Therefore, we need to work with all children with disabilities. For our society, both happiness and success are considered. The existing system of education of children with disabilities at home, boarding school and other special state institutions provides the child with the opportunity to receive a sufficiently high-quality education, but due to the lack of communication skills, this knowledge is not required. goes In this way, the society loses its material and spiritual wealth, and a person with limited opportunities

loses the society, becomes lonely, unable to join his relatives, becomes shy and shy. Until our government decides to take control of this problem, the situation will continue and our children's thinking will remain stunted. This assistance has become an even stronger necessity due to its limitations. The National Concept of the inclusive education model was developed within the framework of the "Inclusive education in Uzbekistan" project. According to experts and specialists, this model is of particular importance due to its modernity. This model was recognized as successful and effective by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The participants of the inclusive education system are:

- In the family: Parents
- In educational institutions: pedagogues and educators with their talent and knowledge, defectologists for eliminating language defects in children;
- healthy and disabled children;
- non-governmental non-commercial public organizations.

Activities of children with special needs, other children, teachers and educators have a special place in inclusive education. Thanks to this kind of education, children with special needs: meet their physical, mental and intellectual needs, learn educational materials that take into account their capabilities, actively participate in various games with their friends and peers. Physical health is important in the lives of children with disabilities, especially at a young age. In the process of protecting the preserved health of the child, it is necessary and necessary to positively solve the issue of forming life skills in order to develop and ensure the duration of his healthy life step by step. scientific-methodical and practical approach to the issue of travel, the issue of improving knowledge and skills is of great importance. For this, it is necessary to develop a system of management and control of the pedagogical process, effective methods, methods and means of ensuring children's physical development. We hope that the efforts made by our state and society to increase the opportunities of children with disabilities, to introduce the principle of integration and participation will bring good results and, in turn, will require their development and timely elimination of their problems. In our opinion, there are enough problems waiting to be solved in this area. In working with children involved in inclusive education, it is necessary and appropriate to implement it step by step, based on the principles of individuality. Taking into account the physical and mental condition of each child, we must achieve a place among his peers by developing his existing capabilities. Otherwise, the results may not have the desired effect or worsen the child's health. In our opinion, first of all, it is necessary to clearly determine the level of disabilities and developmental stages of children with disabilities who can be involved in inclusive

education based on medical, psychological-pedagogical, scientific criteria. Based on the results, it would be appropriate to develop guidelines for inclusive education.

In conclusion, I would like to say that if we apply inclusive education to preschool children and primary school students, we will achieve good results. we need to develop many new projects. It is necessary to involve disabled, deaf, deaf, and language-impaired children in education. Only then will the society develop, only then will they live a happy life. Based on this, we must develop inclusive education at a stronger level. Supporting inclusive education in our society will make it more means to raise one step.

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